

Mixed Model Analysis

[DataSet1] /Users/atom/Library/Mobile Documents/com~apple~CloudDocs/Desktop/PhD Docs/Main study/OWM_1.2.sav

Mixed Model Analysis

		Model Dimension ^a		
		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1		1
	Doctor * Propensity_c	1		1
	Patient * Propensity_c	1		1
	Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		12		14

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b		
	Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w		
	Doctor * Propensity_c		
	Patient * Propensity_c		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	571.082566
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	583.082566
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	583.297400
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	613.001278
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	607.001278

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	19.418	1299.435	<.001
Patient	1	19.604	15818.969	<.001
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1	16.058	.235	.635
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1	19.824	2.126	.160
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1	23.722	35.109	<.001
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1	180.041	112.871	<.001
Doctor * Propensity_c	1	11.770	1.771	.208
Patient * Propensity_c	1	198.067	8.339	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.814	.106	19.418	36.048	<.001	3.593
Patient	3.996	.032	19.604	125.773	<.001	3.930
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.156	.322	16.058	.484	.635	-.527
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	-.401	.275	19.824	-1.458	.160	-.975
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.516	.087	23.722	5.925	<.001	.336
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	.475	.045	180.041	10.624	<.001	.386
Doctor * Propensity_c	.130	.098	11.770	1.331	.208	-.083
Patient * Propensity_c	.089	.031	198.067	2.888	.004	.028

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.035
Patient	4.063
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.839
Doctor * TrustworthinessParticular_w	.173
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.696
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	.563
Doctor * Propensity_c	.343
Patient * Propensity_c	.150

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.122	.013	9.572	<.001	.099
	Var(2)	.384	.040	9.595	<.001	.313
	Corr(2,1)	.099	.074	1.342	.180	-.047
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.073	.042	1.718	.086	.023
	Var(2)	.004	.005	.658	.511	.000
	Corr(2,1)	-.684	.742	-.922	.357	-.998

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.150
	Var(2)	.472
	Corr(2,1)	.241
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.228
	Var(2)	.070
	Corr(2,1)	.956

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * Propensity_c	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		9		11

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b		
	Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w		
	Patient * Propensity_c		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	569.839658
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	581.839658
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	582.052856
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	611.803426
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	605.803426

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.213	2324.177	<.001
Patient	1	19.322	15635.870	<.001
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	1	23.713	34.585	<.001
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	1	181.246	112.681	<.001
Patient * Propensity_c	1	197.708	8.165	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.912	.081	16.213	48.210	<.001	3.740
Patient	3.995	.032	19.322	125.043	<.001	3.928
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.515	.088	23.713	5.881	<.001	.334
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	.475	.045	181.246	10.615	<.001	.387
Patient * Propensity_c	.088	.031	197.708	2.857	.005	.027

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.084
Patient	4.062
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_b	.696
Patient * TrustworthinessParticular_w	.563
Patient * Propensity_c	.149

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.122	.013	9.579	<.001	.099
	Var(2)	.383	.040	9.615	<.001	.312
	Corr(2,1)	.100	.074	1.350	.177	-.046
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.079	.041	1.929	.054	.029
	Var(2)	.004	.006	.671	.502	.000
	Corr(2,1)	-.299	.639	-.468	.640	-.933

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.150
	Var(2)	.469
	Corr(2,1)	.242
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.218
	Var(2)	.069
	Corr(2,1)	.788

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * Propensity_c	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		9		11

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b		
	Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w		
	Patient * Propensity_c		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	603.418567
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	615.418567
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	615.631765
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	645.382335
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	639.382335

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.204	2314.089	<.001
Patient	1	16.608	12661.860	<.001
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	1	24.847	15.121	<.001
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	1	198.595	61.712	<.001
Patient * Propensity_c	1	196.665	8.528	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.911	.081	16.204	48.105	<.001	3.739
Patient	4.071	.036	16.608	112.525	<.001	3.995
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	.384	.099	24.847	3.889	<.001	.181
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	.354	.045	198.595	7.856	<.001	.265
Patient * Propensity_c	.098	.033	196.665	2.920	.004	.032

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ... Upper Bound
Doctor	4.083
Patient	4.148
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_b	.588
Patient * BenevolenceParticular_w	.443
Patient * Propensity_c	.163

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.141	.015	9.625	<.001	.115
	Var(2)	.383	.040	9.617	<.001	.312
	Corr(2,1)	.085	.074	1.145	.252	-.061
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.079	.041	1.929	.054	.029
	Var(2)	.009	.008	1.148	.251	.002
	Corr(2,1)	-.002	.478	-.004	.997	-.735

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.173
	Var(2)	.469
	Corr(2,1)	.228
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.219
	Var(2)	.048
	Corr(2,1)	.733

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * Propensity_c	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_b		
	Doctor * IntegrityParticular_w		
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_b		
	Patient * IntegrityParticular_w		
	Patient * Propensity_c		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	585.136444
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	597.136444
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	597.350730
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	627.070212
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	621.070212

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.132	.014	9.596	<.001	.107
	Var(2)	.384	.040	9.615	<.001	.313
	Corr(2,1)	.128	.073	1.743	.081	-.018
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.071	.039	1.795	.073	.024
	Var(2)	.006	.006	.901	.368	.001
	Corr(2,1)	-.548	.578	-.949	.342	-.977

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.161
	Var(2)	.470
	Corr(2,1)	.268
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.210
	Var(2)	.050
	Corr(2,1)	.763

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	1		1
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	1		1
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	1		1
	Patient * Propensity_c	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		11		13

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b		
	Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w		
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_b		
	Patient * CompetenceParticular_w		
	Patient * Propensity_c		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	589.370823
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	601.370823
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	601.585109
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	631.304592
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	625.304592

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	21.364	320.504	<.001
Patient	1	199.966	10520.229	<.001
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	1	17.191	.263	.614
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	1	20.187	.265	.612
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	1	199.619	50.043	<.001
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	1	199.289	90.117	<.001
Patient * Propensity_c	1	198.909	11.893	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Doctor	3.810	.213	21.364	17.903	<.001	3.368
Patient	3.883	.038	199.966	102.568	<.001	3.808
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	.165	.322	17.191	.513	.614	-.513
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	-.164	.319	20.187	-.515	.612	-.829
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	.457	.065	199.619	7.074	<.001	.329
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	.393	.041	199.289	9.493	<.001	.311
Patient * Propensity_c	.110	.032	198.909	3.449	<.001	.047

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	95% ...
	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.252
Patient	3.957
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_b	.844
Doctor * CompetenceParticular_w	.501
Patient * CompetenceParticular_b	.584
Patient * CompetenceParticular_w	.474
Patient * Propensity_c	.173

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.136	.014	9.973	<.001	.112
	Var(2)	.383	.040	9.622	<.001	.312
	Corr(2,1)	.104	.074	1.402	.161	-.042
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.090	.047	1.923	.054	.033
	Var(2)	.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.
	Corr(2,1)	.037 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.165
	Var(2)	.470
	Corr(2,1)	.245
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.251
	Var(2)	.
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.